

Consumer communities between online and offline channels: Towards a new conceptualization in b2b thinking

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Introduction

This study investigates how consumption relates to business-to-business (b2b) marketing. The perspective of the Industrial Marketing and Purchasing (IMP) Group is adopted in this paper (Ford et al., 2011). Previous contributions have proposed consumers exclusively as final market players, considering them outside the boundaries of b2b markets. However, some research also posits the opportunity to establish consumer relationships for b2b purposes (Landqvist and Lind, 2019; Keränen et al., 2021). In particular, this paper investigates relationships with consumer communities (Cova, 1997), considering online and offline channels. In this context, digitalization has blurred the boundaries between the virtual and physical world, shedding light on the need to understand how digital and physical relationships intertwine.

Methods

The study's exploratory nature led us to adopt a qualitative methodology based on a multiple-case study approach (Eisenhardt, 1989; Yin, 2003). In particular, we conducted face-to-face semi-structured interviews with the founder entrepreneurs of eight Italian fashion companies. A fundamental requirement for identifying companies was having a relationship with consumer communities for business purposes. To this aim, we consulted secondary materials, e.g., news about the companies published in newspapers and specialized magazines, firms' websites, and social reports. We also monitored the online activity of the companies.

Results

The study aims to fill a gap in the extant literature by advancing a new conceptualization of consumer communities in the b2b domain. We state that these communities can act as business actors and actively relate with companies in business-to-business networks. Therefore, we propose that

communities can be conceived simultaneously as consumers of the final market and players in the b2b market. Moreover, while contacts between companies and consumer communities develop mainly through online channels, consumers become central business actors for organizations offline.

References

- Cova, B., 1997. Community and consumption: Towards a definition of the “linking value” of product or services. *European Journal of Marketing*, 31(3/4), 297-316.
- Eisenhardt, K. M., 1989. Building theories from case study research. *Academy of Management Review*, 14(4), 532-550.
- Ford, D., Gadde, L. E., Hakansson, H., Snehota, I., 2011. *Managing business relationships*. United Kingdom, Chichester.
- Keränen, O., Komulainen, H., Lehtimäki, T., Ulkuniemi, P., 2021. Restructuring existing value networks to diffuse sustainable innovations in food packaging. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 93, 509-519.
- Landqvist, M., Lind, F., 2019. A start-up embedding in three business network settings - A matter of resource combining. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 80, 160-171.
- Yin, R., 2003. *Case study research: Design and methods*. California, Thousand Oaks.

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